

ISic0999

I.Sicily inscription 0999

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary; votive (?)

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 118

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]ζῶον ἔχων ὕδωρ
2. [---] εἰς μνημόσυνον
3. [---] αἰώνιον ὑπὲρ εὐχῆ[ς]
4. [---] τῶν δεσποτῶν αὐτοῦ
5. [---] Ὑγεῖνος κα[ὶ] ΠΣΝΥΑΔΙΣ

Apparatus

Text of IG with slight changes based on Kaibel's diplomatic transcription

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492626

EDCS 39102153

PHI 140477

Bibliography

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